

Together,
there's
something
science
can do.

Issue Tracker 2025/08 August 19, 2025

[Novartis teams up with Atropos Health to speed rare disease diagnosis with AI](#) : The new partnership will initially focus on developing AI models that identify individuals who may have paroxysmal nocturnal hemoglobinuria (PNH). Researchers have come up [with an initial AI model](#) that has shown promise in detecting the disease earlier by analyzing symptoms such as anemia, age, hemoglobin, creatinine, and haptoglobin counts. With PNH affecting only 10–20 people per million and often taking years to diagnose, earlier detection could reduce complications and improve patient care.

[Using generative AI, researchers design compounds that can kill drug-resistant bacteria](#) : MIT researchers report using generative AI to design novel antibiotics capable of combating drug-resistant bacteria, including Neisseria [gonorrhoeae](#) and multi-drug-resistant [Staphylococcus aureus](#) (MRSA). Using two AI approaches, fragment-based and unconstrained molecule generation, they discovered compounds such as NG1, effective against drug-resistant gonorrhea, and DN1, which cleared MRSA infections in mice. The research, part of MIT's Antibiotics-AI Project and in collaboration with Phare Bio, hints at AI's potential to explore previously inaccessible chemical spaces and accelerate the development of new antibiotics for resistant infections.

[Lilly signs \\$1.3 billion deal with Superluminal to discover obesity medicines using AI](#) : Under the deal, Superluminal will employ its AI platform to identify potential drug candidates, while Eli Lilly will have exclusive rights to develop and commercialize any resulting prescription medicines. The agreement includes upfront and milestone payments, an equity investment, and royalties on net sales of approved drugs. This partnership illustrates Eli Lilly's interest AI-assisted drug development amid competition from Novo Nordisk, which recently expanded access to its diabetes and weight-loss treatments in the U.S. and gained regulatory approval for Wegovy to treat advanced liver disease.

[National rare disease effort among those upended by Trump's freeze on Harvard grants](#) : The NIH's freeze on grants to Harvard University under the Trump administration has disrupted critical research programs, including the Undiagnosed Diseases Network (UDN), which diagnoses rare and unexplained illnesses. Harvard holds UDN's central \$4.2 million grant, and the freeze has halted patient matching, genome analysis, and model organism research, leaving staff unable to work and layoffs likely. These cuts occur amid broader threats to biomedical research funding, [including proposed caps on indirect costs, which risk putting in peril the development of treatments for rare genetic disorders](#), leaving patients and underfunded disease areas particularly vulnerable.